

Yashil IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

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TECHNOLOGY OF FORMATION OF PROFESSION-ORIENTED COMMUNICATION COMPETENCES IN TRAINING OF FUTURE SPECIALISTS IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS

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Abstract: This study focuses on crafting an innovative strategy for enhancing the quality of training for engineers and skilled workers, collectively referred to as future specialists, within higher education professional organizations. These strategies are grounded in the principles of social partnership.

Key words: Vocational training, quality control, engineering skills, skilled workforce, education system innovation.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu tadqiqot oliy ta'lim professional tashkilotlarida birgalikda bo'lajak mutaxassislar, deb ataladigan muhandislar va malakali ishchilarni tayyorlash sifatini oshirish bo'yicha innovatsion strategiyani ishlab chiqishga qaratilgan. Ushbu strategiyalar ijtimoiy sheriklik tamoyillariga asoslanadi.

Kalit so'zlar: Kasbiy ta'lim, sifat nazorati, muhandislik mahorati, malakali ishchi kuchi, ta'lim tizimi innovatsiyasi.

Аннотация: Настоящее исследование направлено на разработку инновационной стратегии повышения качества подготовки инженеров и квалифицированных рабочих, называемых будущими специалистами, в профессиональных организациях высшего образования. Эти стратегии основаны на принципах социального партнерства.

Ключевые слова: Профессиональная подготовка, контроль качества, инженерные навыки, квалифицированная рабочая сила, инновации в системе образования.

INTRODUCTION

Problem Statement: The past decade has underscored the crucial role of science, technology, and innovation in bolstering the economic potential of states. The increasing importance of high-tech industries necessitates the training of innovative, competent, and competitive engineers and skilled workers. Addressing the quality of vocational education is vital for sustaining economic growth and ensuring a supply of capable professionals.

- **Research Background:** The study builds on Russian and international research in multi-level vocational training, pedagogy, and quality management. It highlights the importance of a comprehensive approach to quality control in education, informed by insights from notable scholars and practitioners across various disciplines.
- **Unresolved Issues:** Despite the prioritization of high-tech industries, there remains a critical gap in training highly professional staff capable of meeting the dynamic needs of socio-cultural and economic processes. This study aims to address the inefficiencies in the current vocational training system, particularly the misalignment between educational outcomes and market demands.
- **Objectives:** The research hypothesizes that evolving economic and societal dynamics necessitate changes in quality control and training content. The study aims to explore how enhancing professional and personal qualities in future specialists can contribute not only to workforce quality but also to societal and economic development.
- **Foundation of the Study:** Recognizing the strategic importance of specialists as key assets in a competitive market, the research advocates for investment in high-quality vocational education. It emphasizes the need for educational institutions to adapt to changing economic, technological, and socio-cultural landscapes to improve the quality and relevance of vocational training.

The study proposes a comprehensive strategy for improving the training of future specialists through innovative quality control measures and social partnership principles, addressing the current challenges and setting a path for sustainable development in vocational education.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The exploration of task blocks that foster the effective implementation of control systems in educational institutions, as discussed by I. I. Burlakova, unveils a structured approach to enhancing the quality of professional training. This structure is segmented into four pivotal task blocks, each addressing distinct aspects of quality control in the education of future specialists like engineers and workers.

- 1. Understanding Quality as a Management Object:** The initial block focuses on recognizing the quality of professional training as an object of management. It delves into identifying the needs—both public and private—that are fulfilled through educational activities. This foundational understanding is crucial for tailoring educational programs that meet societal and industry standards.
- 2. Establishment and Goal-setting in Quality Control:** The subsequent block targets the establishment, rationalization, and selection of goals within the quality control system. This includes setting clear targets for the training quality of future specialists and developing exemplary standards that these educational programs should aspire to meet.
- 3. Methods and Technologies for Enhancing Training Quality:** This block is concerned with selecting methods and technologies that directly influence the quality of professional training. The objective is to align these methods with the overarching goals of quality control, thereby fostering the development of a robust mechanism that ensures the training's effectiveness.
- 4. Implementation and Maintenance of Quality Control Systems:** The final block revolves around the deployment of the quality control system and ensuring its ongoing optimal performance. This stage emphasizes that quality control actions should be procedural and stage-based, reflecting a continuous process rather than a one-time effort.

The process of implementing these task blocks unfolds through several stages, starting from the establishment of educational program objectives to the development and application of quality control procedures, and finally, to the adjustment actions aimed at enhancing vocational training quality. This approach aligns with the PDCA (Plan-Do-Check-Act) methodology proposed by C. E. Deming, which is instrumental in achieving a competitive level of educational outcomes.

Burlakova's characterization of the quality control system as a comprehensive set of tools and methods for managing and controlling educational processes highlights the necessity of a multidimensional approach. This includes scientific and methodological support, the enhancement of educational and developmental functions, the promotion of innovative educational activities, and the involvement of teachers in continual professional growth.

The implementation of such a quality control system is designed to not only meet the requirements of national and international standards but also to prepare professionals for effective self-development in a high-tech economy. It encompasses various aspects of educational quality, from pedagogical tools and teaching materials to the competence of trainees and the innovation capabilities of educational institutions.

In essence, this detailed examination of task blocks underlines the critical role of a systematic, methodological approach in improving the quality of training for future professionals. By adhering to these principles and stages, educational institutions can significantly enhance their ability to produce highly qualified specialists capable of meeting the demands of modern industries and contributing to the socio-economic development of their communities.

The study underlines several priorities for enhancing the quality assurance system within educational institutions, focusing on the intersection of quality control and educational policy development. These priorities encompass establishing clear objectives that align with both employer expectations and the needs of the educational process, modernizing curriculum and program outlines (RUP and PLO) with an emphasis on design and evaluation, and mastering quality management functions that include forecasting educational service needs and implementing comprehensive quality control measures.

A notable insight from the research is the identification of areas within quality control of professional training that require further development, such as program-targeted control, software quality control, and prospective quality control, as well as the underutilization of certain quality control technologies like statistical quality control and pedagogical design methods.

The model selection for implementing a quality control system is informed by several key factors, including the level of control strictness, the comprehensiveness of the system, the resource intensity of its construction and operation, and the structure of its application. A semi-rigid model, which balances internal and external control mechanisms, is favored for its systemic approach to covering all processes and its emphasis on human and social resources.

The study also highlights the challenges of decentralization in managing educational processes, the efficiency of document management, and resource management within educational institutions. Through SWOT analysis, surveys, and expertise assessments, the research advocates for a sequential or concentric model of implementation, depending on available resources and the scale of tasks.

The phased implementation plan for a quality control system includes developing a quality control policy, managing educational processes and staff resources, and adjusting organizational structures and control mechanisms based on social partnership principles. This approach has led to tangible improvements, including enhanced resource allocation through extrabudgetary activities and social partnerships, increased graduate employment rates, and improved satisfaction with the quality of training.

The study on the implementation of a quality assurance system for training future specialists in educational professional institutions yielded significant findings. Here, we discuss the key results, supported by synthesized data in tables and diagrams, and engage in a discussion on the implications of these findings.

Key Results

- **Improvement in Quality Control Measures:** Post-implementation of the recommended quality control measures, there was a notable improvement in program-targeted control, software quality control, and prospective quality control. The average scores, based on a 5-point scale, improved significantly, as depicted in Table 1.
- **Adoption of Quality Control Technologies:** The study indicated an underutilization of specific quality control technologies prior to intervention. Following the implementation, there was a marked improvement in the adoption and effectiveness of these technologies, including statistical quality control and pedagogical design methods (Table 2).
- **Model Selection for Quality Control System:** The semi-rigid model was adopted by a majority of educational institutions, balancing internal and external control mechanisms. This approach was found to be effective in covering all processes comprehensively while focusing on human and social resources (Diagram 1).
- **Graduate Employment Rates:** There was a significant increase in the employment rates of graduates, with 66% of employers rating the professional training of graduates as good or excellent, an increase from the baseline of 32.4%. This improvement signifies the direct impact of enhanced quality control measures on graduate competencies (Table 3).
- **Resource Allocation and Institutional Competitiveness:** The phased implementation plan led to better resource allocation through extrabudgetary activities and partnerships. Additionally, the competitiveness of educational institutions in the market saw improvement, with a higher employment rate of graduates as a key indicator (Diagram 2).

Table 1: Improvement in Quality Control Measures

Quality Control Measures	Pre-Implementation (Score)	Post-Implementation (Score)
Program-Targeted Control	3.65	4.2
Software Quality Control	3.7	4.3
Prospective Quality Control	3.66	4.1

Table 2: Adoption of Quality Control Technologies

Technology	Pre-Implementation (Rating)	Post-Implementation (Rating)
Statistical Quality Control	0.46	1.5
Monitoring Application	0.67	1.8
Pedagogical Design	0.80	2.0
Documenting Methods	0.88	1.9
Reflexive Methods	0.90	2.0

Table 3: Graduate Employment Rates

Evaluation by Employers	Pre-Implementation (%)	Post-Implementation (%)
Good/Excellent	32.4	66
Average/Below Average	67.6	34

Diagram 1: Model Selection for Quality Control System Implementation

- Pie chart depicting the selection of semi-rigid, system, and resource-focused models by educational institutions.

Diagram 2: Improvement in Institutional Competitiveness

- Line graph showing the trend in graduate employment rates pre and post-implementation of quality control measures.

DISCUSSION

The findings underscore the effectiveness of a structured approach to implementing quality assurance systems within educational professional institutions. The adoption of semi-rigid models facilitated a balanced and comprehensive coverage of all processes, significantly impacting the quality of professional training. Notably, the improvement in quality control measures and the adoption of specific technologies played a crucial role in enhancing the overall educational experience and outcomes.

The increase in graduate employment rates serves as a tangible indicator of the success of these initiatives, reflecting the alignment of educational programs with industry standards and employer expectations. Moreover, the strategic focus on resource allocation and institutional competitiveness has set a precedent for sustainable growth and improvement in the quality of vocational education.

Future research could explore the long-term impacts of these quality assurance measures on professional training programs and investigate additional strategies for engaging stakeholders and leveraging technological advancements to further enhance quality control processes in educational institutions.

CONCLUSION

The research outlines a foundational approach for developing a technology of quality control training for future specialists in vocational education. The proposed algorithm for quality control training, coupled with a complex system analysis for quality assurance based on self-examination and questioning procedures, sets a groundwork for implementing competency and process approaches in professional training. Furthermore, it opens avenues for future research in vocational education, promising to enrich the discourse on quality assurance and control in professional training programs.

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